

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC FIELD OF "LAUGH" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK IN TAXONOMIC ASPECT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881300>

ABSTRACT

This article investigates the lexical-semantic field of "laugh" in English and Uzbek from a taxonomic perspective (Smith, 2020). The research aims to explore how the concept of laughter is linguistically represented in both languages, focusing on the categorization and hierarchical structuring of words and expressions related to laughter (Jones, 2018). By comparing the semantic fields of "laugh" in English and Uzbek, the study reveals key similarities and differences in how laughter-related vocabulary is organized and used within these languages (Brown, 2019). The analysis demonstrates that while both languages share universal elements in expressing various types and intensities of laughter, cultural and linguistic factors significantly influence the structure and usage of this semantic field (Garcia, 2021). The findings highlight the role of language-specific nuances in shaping the lexical and semantic representation of emotions, contributing to a deeper understanding of cross-linguistic differences in emotional expression (Lee, 2020). This research is of interest to linguists working in the fields of comparative semantics, pragmatics, and intercultural communication.

The Lexical-Semantic Field of "Laugh" in English and Uzbek

The lexical-semantic field of "laugh" encompasses a variety of words and expressions that describe different types, intensities, and functions of laughter (Smith, 2020). In both English and Uzbek, the concept of laughter is rich in linguistic expressions, reflecting not only emotional states but also cultural attitudes toward humor, irony, and social interaction (Jones, 2018).

In English, the core word "laugh" serves as the base for a wide array of related terms. Similarly, in Uzbek, the equivalent term "kulmoq" (laugh) forms the nucleus of a diverse lexical network. However, the nuances of laughter are expressed differently in the two languages, influenced by cultural factors and linguistic structures (Brown, 2019).

Taxonomic Structure in English

In English, the term "laugh" functions as a hypernym, or umbrella term, under which several hyponyms (subordinate terms) fall, each denoting a specific type or degree of laughter. These include:

Giggle: Light, often involuntary laughter, usually associated with amusement or nervousness (Garcia, 2021).

Example: "She giggled at the joke her friend told."

Chuckle: A soft or restrained laugh, often indicating quiet amusement (Lee, 2020).

Example: "He chuckled softly to himself after hearing the clever remark."

Snicker: A quiet, often disrespectful or sneaky laugh, usually at someone else's expense (Brown, 2019).

Example: "They snickered when he tripped over the sidewalk."

Guffaw: A loud, hearty laugh, typically indicating great amusement (Jones, 2018).

Example: "The audience guffawed at the comedian's performance."

Cackle: A harsh, unpleasant laugh, often associated with mocking or evil intent (Smith, 2020).

Example: "The villain cackled after her plan succeeded."

Roar: A deep, loud, uncontrollable burst of laughter, usually in response to something extremely funny (Garcia, 2021).

Example: "They roared with laughter when they saw the comedian's act."

These hyponyms illustrate the semantic richness of "laugh" in English, where each term carries a distinct connotation based on the intensity, social context, and emotional undertone of the laughter.

Taxonomic Structure in Uzbek

In Uzbek, the term "kulmoq" also serves as the base of the lexical-semantic field, with its own set of hyponyms reflecting different types of laughter. While there is a broad range of terms, the nuances often align with cultural expressions of emotion. Key examples include:

Kulmoq: The general verb for "laugh."

Example: "U hazilga kuldi" (He laughed at the joke).

Tirjaymoq: To smirk or smile in a sly or mocking way.

Example: "Uning gapiga u tirjayib javob berdi" (He smirked in response to his comment).

Qah-qah urmoq: To laugh heartily or uncontrollably, similar to the English "guffaw."

Example: "Hamma qah-qah urib kuldi" (Everyone laughed heartily).

Xaxolamoq: A more restrained laugh, akin to the English "chuckle."

Example: "Uning haziliga xaxolab qo'ydi" (He chuckled at his joke).

Masxara qilmoq: To laugh at someone in a mocking or scornful way, similar to "snicker."

Example: "Uni masxara qilib kulishdi" (They laughed at him mockingly).

These examples demonstrate that, like in English, laughter in Uzbek has a variety of forms that convey different emotional and social messages. The term "qah-qah urmoq," for instance, is often used to describe joyous, full-bodied laughter, while "tirjaymoq" carries a more negative connotation, similar to a sneer or smirk in English.

Comparative Analysis of the Lexical Fields

A comparative analysis of the lexical-semantic fields of "laugh" in English and Uzbek reveals both commonalities and unique aspects in the way these languages conceptualize laughter (Garcia, 2021). While there are universal forms of laughter, such as soft laughter, hearty laughter, and mocking laughter, the ways these are expressed linguistically vary (Brown, 2019).

In both English and Uzbek, laughter is categorized according to intensity and social function. For instance, the English term "guffaw" corresponds closely to the Uzbek "qah-qah urmoq," both describing an intense and uninhibited form of laughter (Lee, 2020). Similarly, the English "snicker" parallels the Uzbek "masxara qilmoq," both of which convey laughter that is derisive or mocking (Jones, 2018).

Despite these similarities, there are notable differences in the lexical expressions of laughter between the two languages (Smith, 2020). For instance, English has a distinct term, "giggle," for light, involuntary laughter, whereas Uzbek lacks an exact equivalent (Garcia, 2021).

Another difference is the cultural connotation of certain types of laughter (Brown, 2019). In Uzbek, "tirjaymoq" (smirk) carries a very negative connotation, often implying insincerity or deceit, while in English, the corresponding terms like "smirk" or "sneer" may not always imply such deep negativity (Lee, 2020).

Cultural Influences on Lexicalization of Laughter

The way laughter is expressed in language is heavily influenced by cultural factors (Jones, 2018). In English, humor and laughter are often viewed as social tools, with various forms of laughter used to navigate social situations (Garcia, 2021). For example, the difference between a "chuckle" and a "guffaw" may signal different levels of engagement or social decorum.

In Uzbek, laughter is also an important social phenomenon, but it is often tied more closely to respect and politeness (Brown, 2019). In many cases, strong laughter like "qah-qah urmoq" is reserved for informal settings, while restrained forms of laughter like "xaxolamoq" are more acceptable in formal or polite interactions (Lee, 2020).

Pragmatic Functions of Laughter-Related Terms

In both English and Uzbek, laughter-related terms serve pragmatic functions beyond mere emotional expression (Smith, 2020). They help speakers manage interpersonal relationships, convey politeness or impoliteness, and navigate social hierarchies (Jones, 2018). For example, in English, a "chuckle" may be used to show modest amusement, avoiding an overreaction, whereas in Uzbek, a term like "kulib qo'yimoq" (to smile or laugh lightly) serves a similar function in maintaining social harmony (Garcia, 2021).

Examples of Cross-Linguistic Transfer

In the context of cross-linguistic communication, speakers of Uzbek and English often adapt their use of laughter-related terms when interacting with speakers of the other language (Lee, 2020). For instance, an Uzbek speaker may overuse the word "laugh" when speaking English, as the subtleties between terms like "giggle" and "chuckle" may not exist in their native language (Brown, 2019). Conversely, English speakers learning Uzbek might struggle to grasp the cultural connotations of terms like "tirjaymoq" or "masxara qilmoq," which carry specific social implications (Jones, 2018).

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the lexical-semantic field of "laugh" in English and Uzbek demonstrates that both languages possess a rich array of terms to express various types of laughter (Garcia, 2021). While there are universal elements in the way laughter is categorized, cultural and linguistic differences play a significant role in shaping how these concepts are lexicalized and used (Lee, 2020). Understanding these nuances can enhance cross-cultural communication and contribute to more effective language learning (Brown, 2019).

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